

Qualities of Student-Examinees of Bukidnon State University College Admission Test

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Abstract— *Qualities of students are important aspects that would determine success or failure in studying a college course. The purpose of this study was to describe the characteristics of students who took the College Admission Test. It used data mining and descriptive methods of research using the personal information sheet of students who took the College Admission Test. The data were subjected to Factor Analysis which reduced the number of variables into fewer factors namely Scholastic-Economic, Paternal Work-Related, Socio-Demographic, Socio-Academic Achievement and Developmental-Aptitude Factors.*

Keywords— *Qualities, Student-Examinees, College Admission Test.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Admission tests are valuable measures of student achievement. College admission test has important consequences for the individual test. By learning these characteristics, you may better understand the day-to-day and class-to-class behavior of successful students. Most colleges and universities use the test scores as a means of assessing a candidate for admission. Other criteria included in this assessment are the high school grade point average (GPA), rank in class, record of extracurricular and service activities, letters of recommendation, applicant's essay, evidence of persistence, and interviews, which assist the college or university in determining the applicant's maturity, determination, personality, and character. High school GPAs are considered a "soft" measure because grading standards range as widely as they do in college.

The combination of high school GPAs and entrance test scores is very useful in determining admissions because it provides different kinds of information about the academic performance of students. It also provides reliable and efficient information that is very useful means of helping them to make a better selection of the candidates to enter college. More so, to enhance these spirited young individuals to be socially and mentally competent members of society.

Over the years, college entrance tests have improved considerably. Colleges and universities have determined that students who do well on the tests have the ability to succeed in college. These tests, however, are indicators only of a student's can do college work; they cannot measure perseverance and interest in learning. The first and foremost important quality of a good student is, of course, hard working. We can't have a good result in academic success without training and effort. Vladimir I. Lenin claimed that "learn, learn more, learn forever", that shows us the importance of learning in our whole lifetime regardless of age. Knowledge is not inborn but

experienced, not unchanged but keep-up-date, and not easy but hard to earn, and those who are not willing enough to face challenges and those who don't have passion for working would not come to achieve their goals and succeed in their lives.

Wang (2011) accentuated that college entrance examination policies are the criteria developed by the government and institutions of higher education for the authoritative distribution and regulation of higher education opportunities. This is found to be the most important factor affecting equality of access to higher education.

The next quality is active in community. A good student should be highly appreciated not only by his academic success but by his social activities as well. In other words, a good person should be measured not only by what is he doing well for himself but also by what is he contributing the community. Also, an active student means a communicative skillful person in life and thus he is widening the chances to make friends with everybody around him and this is to a good thing we always want to, so that his college-life should be more fun and his confidence increasingly grow up.

Last but not least quality of a good student is well-prepared for the future. Every student is taught to have ambitious and to keep the high dream, yet he should know how to let his dream meets reality, and he should be practical and realistic because life is not fair and every step to success takes time and patience. All students have to do right now for school is a good preparation for every step with a careful plan and always keep in mind that failure is one thing that he should have to face and overcome to gain experiences and to achieve goals.

In conclusion, a good student should have all qualities mentioned above, and even more other quality to be good and complete student. A hard-working student tells us his passion; an active student tells us his social responsibilities; and a well-prepared student tells us his abilities. Every student should have all of these qualities to be a good student.

II. OBJECTIVES

The purpose of this study was to look into the characteristics and qualities of students taking the College Admission Test relative to their socio-demographic, economic and academic-aptitude achievement status. Specifically, it aimed to describe the specific various variables into a fewer factors that generally represent the status and description of student-examinees.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study used data mining and descriptive methods of research using the data from the personal information sheet of students who took the Bukidnon State University College Admission Test (BSUCAT). Data were primarily taken from the Office of Admission and Testing of the Bukidnon State University. The data which contained the socio-demographic, economic and academic-aptitude performance of student-examinees were subjected to Factor Analysis using the Minitab statistical software. This was done to group similar variables and describe its characteristics within the group.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 presents the profile of student-examinees as to their socio-economic and academic aspects.

Factor Loadings and Communalities of Variables per Factor

Factor1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Factor 5
Scholastic-Economic	Paternal Work-Related	Socio-Demographic	Socio-Academic Achievement	Developmental-Aptitude
Math English Filipino Science HS Ave Parents' Income	Father's Occupation	Gender Type of School Mother's Occupation	Type of Residence Highest Educational Attainment	Age CAT Result

Results and Discussions

Table 2

Rotated Factor Loadings and Communalities
Varimax Rotation

Variable	Factor1	Factor2	Factor3	Factor4	Factor5	Communality
Residenc	-0.054	-0.089	0.117	0.926	0.031	0.883
Gender	0.372	-0.026	0.465	-0.053	-0.320	0.461
School	0.251	0.153	0.375	0.083	0.291	0.318
HEA	-0.123	-0.798	-0.168	0.046	-0.055	0.685
Math	0.648	0.126	0.234	-0.086	-0.132	0.515
Eng	0.736	0.100	-0.143	-0.071	0.183	0.611
Fil	0.737	-0.114	0.193	0.234	-0.090	0.656
Sci	0.844	0.034	0.077	0.007	0.066	0.724
Income	0.109	-0.331	-0.608	0.046	-0.139	0.512
Mother	0.171	0.005	0.714	0.117	-0.034	0.555
Father	0.351	0.528	-0.218	0.394	-0.016	0.605
Age	0.055	-0.769	-0.144	0.102	0.166	0.654
Ave	0.914	0.093	0.143	0.005	0.033	0.866
Exam	0.030	-0.121	0.041	0.003	0.875	0.782
Variance	3.4411	1.7120	1.4868	1.1183	1.0685	8.8267
% Var	0.246	0.122	0.106	0.080	0.076	0.630

Table 2 presents the factor loadings and communalities of the variables. It can be gleaned that academic performance of student-examinees in Math, English, Science, Filipino and their high school average as well as their parent's income yielded the highest positive loadings in Factor 1 than in any other factor. These variables refer to academic performance and economic status of student-examinees which we labelled as *Scholastic-Economic Factor*. This indicates that academic grades and parental income of student-examinees are having common characteristics which are one factor being considered when looking at the general characteristics of those students may it be fresh graduates from high school or transferees who took the College Admission Test of the University. This could be because the academic performance of students has something in connection with the parent's income relative to their scholastic and economic status of individual students.

Factor 2 is shown to have the highest positive loading with Father's Occupation being the only variable which belonged

to the second loading. This variable refers to the paternal income related activities which were labelled as *Paternal Work Status Factor*. This means that this variable has nothing in common with other variables. Despite the perceived communality of the variable to the maternal occupation, it still came out as unique. Such peculiarity made this factor an important consideration when looking at the qualities of College Admission Test Examinees. A reason for this could be traced to the extent of significance of father's occupation whether the student's rate of surviving financially to the college education is a success or failure.

Type of School, Gender and Mother's Occupation have the highest positive loadings in Factor 3 when compared among other factors. These variables refer to the socio-demographic aspects of student examinees. This was labelled as *Socio-Demographic Factor*. This indicates that student-examinees' gender, type of school graduated and mother's occupation have shared something in common and which characteristics

are not found in other variables. This made the Factor an important concern when qualities of these students are considered.

Factor 4 has the highest positive loadings with the type of residence and educational attainment. These variables refer to the sociological environment and academic achievement of student – examinees. This was labelled as *Socio-Academic Achievement Factor*. This indicates that sociological upbringing and student’s academic achievement are in common grounds that it should be seriously considered when trying to interpret the general picture of students taking the College Admission Test.

Student’s age and result of the admission examination were in highest positive loading in Factor 5. These two variables refer to the personal development and aptitude information of student-examinees. This was labelled as *Developmental-Aptitude Factor*. This indicates that these variables have characteristics which are shared by both and whose positive loadings should be seriously looked into when personal development and aptitude of students taking the exam are the subjects of inquiry.

In a nutshell, students taking the College Admission Test were characterized as to their scholastic-economic performance, paternal work-related, socio-demographic, socio-academic achievement and developmental-aptitude aspects.

V. CONCLUSION

The College Admission Test as an important tool for the institution to accept quality students. Student-examinees of College Admission Test were found to possess qualities characterized by their scholastic-economic, paternal work

status, socio-demographic profile, socio-academic achievement and developmental-aptitude aspects. Therefore, their characteristics and qualities as student-examinees could be best described along these aspects and of which the Bukidnon State University have seriously considered when deciding about student’s course placement, guidance planning and students’ assistance programs.

The results of the study also provide insights for College Admission Test in-charge and academic heads to continually assess and revise the admission test to improve and refine its discriminant capacities. This will lead the institution to implement policies and guidelines in enhancing the institution’s admission and placement policies and standards.

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